

EFFECTS OF THE ELONGATION PROPERTY OF MATRIX RESIN ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF CP-RESIN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to reveal the effects of the ductile matrix resin and the brittle one in continuous glass fiber mat reinforced CP-resin composites on their mechanical properties and fracture behavior. These two kinds of resins have the characteristic that the elastic modulus and the tensile strength are nearly the same values with each other, while the elongation is different. It is found that elongation property of matrix resin affects remarkably the tensile strength of CP-resin composite but slightly its fracture toughness.

Keywords: Polyesteramide resin, Continuous strand mat, Instrumented impact tensile test, Static fracture toughness, Dynamic fracture toughness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Generally, matrix resin of FRP composite has been shown to be media both for load transmission to a fiber and for load dispersion in a matrix. Hence characteristics of the FRP are influenced by matrix properties. Effects of matrix resin properties on fracture toughness have been mainly studied by delamination. It has been reported by many researchers[1-5] that fracture toughness of matrix resin had influence on the fracture toughness of FRP. However, it is unknown how each property of matrix resin has influence on the property of FRP.

The purpose of this investigation is to examine the role of the matrix resin in the FRP by means of the investigation of mechanical properties and fracture behavior of the composites as a whole. For this purpose we use two types of CP-resins[6] whose elastic modulus and tensile strength are nearly same with each other, while their elongations are very different. The composite specimens are made of these resins and continuous-glass-fiber-mats of 20wt.% and 60wt.% fiber contents. Fiber mats are developed by the deep drawing process so as to reflect elongation property of resin.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Test specimens are made of cross-linked polyesteramide resin (CP-resin) and continuous glass strand mat for reinforcing the resin. CP-resin is the new thermoset resin, developed by Takeda Chemical Industries, LTD.. It is made up of 2,2'-(1,3-phenylene)bis-2-oxazolone (1,3-PBO), dibasic acid and combined with catalyst. The properties of CP-resin vary with the type of dibasic acid and mole ratio: dibasic acid to 1,3-PBO. Two types of resins are used in the present study, i.e., the elastic modulus and the tensile strength are nearly the same values with each other, while the elongation is different, and brittle resin is called H material and the other one is P material. Continuous strand mat are made of spiral and continuous glass fiber(E-glass, 19 μ m diameter). Fiber volume contents of the specimen are 0, 20 and 60wt.% for both resins, and these are called H0, H20, H60, P0, P20 and P60, respectively.

2.2 Static tensile tests of dumbbell specimen

2.2.1 Dumbbell specimen The shape of dumbbell specimens is shown in Fig.1. That shape and dimension are based on JIS standard. Two aluminum plates for the target of laser beams are attached to the test specimen so as to measure its displacement.

2.2.2 Test procedure Static tests are performed using a servo-hydraulic testing machine (Shimadzu, servopulser) at the crosshead speed of 1mm/min. Axial and transverse strain of the specimen are measured by strain gauge, and the change in the gauge length is measured by the laser displacement meter(Keyence, LB-1000) throughout the tests. The tests are carried out under a constant temperature and humidity (20 \pm 2 $^{\circ}$ C,60 \pm 5%RH).

2.3 Tensile tests of SEN specimen

2.3.1 SEN specimen In order to obtain fracture toughness, SEN specimen is used. The shape and dimension of the specimen are shown in Fig. 2. Crack gauge is mounted on the

Fig.1 Geometry of dumbbell type specimen.

Fig.2 Geometry of SEN specimen.

specimen so as to observe crack extension behavior. The notch is carefully cut by a diamond wheel cutter(notch blade, 0.1mm thickness) for both crack gauge and specimen, and notch length a is taken as 1/3 of the specimen width W . The specimen is reinforced with the steel plate over the loading place to prevent the initiation of fracture around the holes.

2.3.2 Test procedure Static tests of SEN specimen are performed by the same

equipment under the same condition to the tests performed to the dumbbell types. Impact test is carried out by the impact testing machine which consists of the load detective equipment based on One Bar Method[7] and the displacement detector of potentiometer, as shown schematically in Fig.3. The specimen is attached between the output bar(steel, 40mm diameter, 4m length) connected to the fixed end and the crosshead moving on the slide rail. The constant impact speed is 3.1m/s, and the impact load in the specimen is calculated from semiconductor gauge located at a distance 250mm from the fitting hole of the output bar. Crack initiation and crack extension behavior are monitored by the crack gauge located at the notch tip. As the loading speed both for the static and the impact testing is comparatively low, the fracture toughness K_s and K_d are calculated by Eq.(1) given by Brown for pin-loading specimen[8].

Fig.3 Schematic of impact testing machine.

$$K_s, K_d = \left(\frac{P \sqrt{a}}{B W} \right) \cdot Y \left(\frac{a}{W} \right) \quad Y \left(\frac{a}{W} \right) = 1.99 - 0.41 \left(\frac{a}{W} \right) + 18.70 \left(\frac{a}{W} \right)^2 - 38.48 \left(\frac{a}{W} \right)^3 + 53.85 \left(\frac{a}{W} \right)^4 \quad (1)$$

where the suffixes s and d imply static and impact condition, P is load, and a , B and W are notch length, thickness and width of the specimen. Y is the correction factor that depends only on a/W .

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Mechanical properties by dumbbell specimen

For each material of H and P , stress-strain curves are shown in Figs.4(a) and 4(b), and elastic modulus E , tensile strength σ_B , elongation δ and Poisson's ratio ν are shown in Tab.1. From these figures and table, E and σ_B of both neat resins(H_0 and P_0) show nearly the same values with each other, but δ of P_0 is 4 times higher than that of H_0 .

For the FRP which consists of these matrix resin, E increases with increasing fiber content expectedly. The values of σ_B for both composites of fiber contents 20wt.%, however, are lower than those of both neat resin materials. The tensile strength of the ductile matrix resin FRP is higher by 20~30% than that of the brittle matrix resin FRP. Thus elongation property of matrix resin contributes to σ_B of the FRP. It is likely that the shearing force induced in the P -matrix FRP by difference in elongation between fiber and resin may be

Fig.4 Stress – strain curves.

Table 1 Mechanical properties.

Material	Fiber content wt.%(vol.%)	Elastic modulus E,GPa	Tensile strength σ_B ,MPa	Elongation δ ,%	Poisson's ratio ν
H0	0 (0)	4.9	91	2.0	0.33
H20	20(11)	8.2	64	0.8	0.38
H60	60(41)	16.7	199	1.5	0.32
P0	0 (0)	4.6	108	8.0	0.37
P20	20(11)	8.4	95	1.2	0.39
P60	60(41)	17.1	275	2.5	0.32

lower than that induced in the H-matrix FRP and the fiber in the P-matrix FRP may bear a less burden so that σ_B of P-matrix FRP becomes to be higher than that of H-matrix FRP.

3.2 FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

3.2.1 Crack extension Figures 5 and 6 show the typical relations between the load-time curves and the crack extension-time curves both for static and impact loading. Observation of crack extension by crack gauge shows that the crack initiates with unstable fracture at P_{max} load and goes into final fracture for P0 and H0 materials, as shown in Figs.5(a) and 6(a). For both matrix resin FRP, as shown in Figs.5(b),(c) and 6(b),(c), after crack extends a few mm, crack extension speed changes drastically to that of unstable fracture near the P_{max} load. It is found from the observation of the fracture surface inked during the course of testing that these crack extensions at early loading time consist mainly of resin cracking and delamination without fiber breaking. In calculating the fracture toughness by Eq.(1), P and a are taken as P_{max} and the initial length of a notch, respectively.

3.2.2 Static and impact fracture toughness Figures 7 and 8 show static fracture toughness K_s and impact fracture toughness K_d obtained by the above method. The values of static and impact fracture toughness (K_s and K_d) increase with increasing fiber content for both matrix resin FRP. K_d for both neat resin materials are less than K_s , but K_d for all FRP are higher than K_s . The fracture toughness of the ductile resin FRP is same or higher than that of the brittle one. Effect of the matrix resin is more notable in respect to K_s rather than K_d , and

Fig.5 Relation between load–time and crack extension–time curves under static loading.

Fig.6 Relation between load–time and crack extension–time curves under impact loading.

Fig.7 Relation between fracture toughness and fiber content under static loading.

Fig.8 Relation between fracture toughness and fiber content under impact loading.

Fig.9 Comparison of fracture surface between under static loading and impact loading.

influence of the impact speed is most prominent in the case of 20wt.% FRP by the reason that rate of change in K_s and K_d is largest among others.

Figure 9 shows SEM photographs which are all taken from the position 2mm distant from the notch tip. It is found that the fracture surface of H0 is rather flat for both static and impact loading, but that the surface of P0 is rough with tear line in comparison with that of H0. The surface of P0 has large mirror zone in the case of impact loading compared with the case of static loading. From these observations, it is recognized that K_s and K_d of P0 are higher than those of H0, and that for both neat resin materials, K_s is higher than K_d .

Fig.9 Comparison of fracture surface between under static loading and impact loading.

As continuous fiber is in the form of spiral and the fiber content is low in the case of 20wt.% FRP, distribution of fiber in a matrix gives a great influence on the morphology of the fracture surface. Over the part where fibers distribute sparsely, the fracture surface is rather flat and we can slightly see resin cracking for H20 material, while the river pattern can be observed for P20 material. On the contrary, over the part where fibers distribute densely or entangle each other, we can see many resin crackings. This tendency is more prominent to H20 material rather than P20 material and also to the impact loading rather than the static one. Thus, morphology of the fracture surface represents difference due to matrix resin, but the value of fracture toughness is almost same or that of P20 material is

slightly higher. Hence, it can be concluded that matrix resin has little influence on fracture toughness.

The fracture surface of 60wt.% FRP shows no difference to both matrix resin FRP and both static and impact loading respectively. However, based on the observation of fracture appearance from the side view, which is not indicated here, the pull-out fiber length of the H60 material is longer than that of the P60 material and also its length is longer in the case of impact loading rather than static loading. Since P-matrix resin is ductile and accommodates itself to deformation well, the pull-out fiber length of P-matrix resin FRP is shorter than that of H-matrix resin FRP.

4. CONCLUSION

Experiments are carried out to study the effects of matrix resin on mechanical properties and fracture behavior of CP-resin FRP. The results obtained are as follows:

- (1) The tensile strength of the ductile matrix resin FRP is higher by 20~30% than that of the brittle matrix resin FRP. Elongation property of matrix resin contributes to σ_B of the FRP.
- (2) The values of static and impact fracture toughness (K_s and K_d) increase with increasing fiber content for both matrix resin FRP.
- (3) The values of K_d for both neat resin materials are less than those of K_s , but K_d for all FRP are higher than K_s .
- (4) The fracture toughness of the ductile resin FRP is same or higher than that of the brittle one. Effect of the matrix resin is more notable in respect to K_s rather than K_d and influence of the impact speed is most prominent in the case of 20wt.% FRP by the reason that rate of change in K_s and K_d is largest among others.

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